

Designing a Roadmap for Effective and Sustainable Strategies for Assessing and Addressing the Challenges of EU Agriculture to Navigate within a Safe and Just Operating Space

Quantity and quality trends of food purchases in France

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Quantity and quality trends of food purchases in France

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Abstract

We analyze the evolution of food purchases for home consumption in France between 2002 and 2019 and examine the implications for both diet quality and environmental outcomes. To do so, we construct a unique longitudinal dataset of French households' food purchases from 2002 to 2019, which we merge with detailed nutritional information and environmental footprint indicators.

Over this period, the total quantity of food purchased increased smoothly by more than 10%. However, aggregate trends mask substantial heterogeneity across food categories. Purchases of cereals, fruits and vegetables, appetizers, and ready-to-eat meals increased markedly, while dairy purchases declined and changes within meat and fish categories were more uneven. Prices also increase by 25% over the whole period. These shifts in food purchases have important nutritional implications. We use the Nutrient Profiling Model (NPM) to assess changes in the nutritional quality of the diet. Our results show increases in both healthy components, such as fruits and vegetables, fiber, and protein, and unhealthy components, particularly sodium. While purchases shift towards products with lower sugar content, total sugar intake increased by about 10% due to larger quantities purchased, suggesting that making better choices does not necessarily result in an overall better diet. The analysis also reveals substantial heterogeneity across food categories. Some food categories appear structurally unhealthy, while others display considerable dispersion, indicating room for substitution within food categories towards healthier products. We also observe substantial heterogeneity across households: the quality of the diet is positively correlated with age and income, and negatively correlated with the obesity status. Finally, in principle, improvements in nutritional quality can be compatible with reductions in environmental impact. While the overall environmental footprint of the diet remained relatively stable over the period, meat, fish, and eggs account for the largest share. Reductions in purchases within these categories would therefore be associated with meaningful improvements in the environmental footprint of diets.

The panel data analysis corroborates and enriches these findings from the graphical analysis. We identify that nutritional quality significantly varies across demographic and socioeconomic groups. Older individuals, wealthier households, and families with young children tend to consume healthier diets. In contrast, obese individuals and those from more modest income groups

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exhibit poorer dietary profiles. While income levels are closely associated with nutritional quality, their influence on environmental outcomes appears insignificant. On the other hand, relative prices have a significant impact, where higher prices of healthy or eco-friendly foods correspond to worse nutritional and environmental outcomes, highlighting the role of affordability in shaping consumption patterns.

These insights carry direct implications for public policy. The deterioration of nutritional quality over time and the disparities observed across population groups call for targeted measures. Policies that support lower-income households in accessing nutrient-dense and sustainably produced foods are pertinent within this context. Fiscal tools such as subsidies on healthy and eco-friendly foods or taxes on ultra-processed, high-sodium products could help shift consumption behaviors. Moreover, increasing awareness about the dual benefits of healthier diets, not only for individual well-being but also for environmental sustainability, can be instrumental in fostering long-term change.

1 Introduction

This report presents a comprehensive analysis of food consumption and its nutritional and environmental qualities in France from 2002 to 2019. By integrating panel data on household food purchases, nutritional indicators (macro- and micronutrient content), and environmental impact metrics for food products, it provides a multidimensional view of the evolution of dietary patterns and their broader implications for health and environmental sustainability.

The study combines descriptive graphical analysis with an econometric approach based on household-level panel data. The econometric models consider variation across time and individuals to identify the determinants of food consumption in terms of quantity, nutritional quality (measured by the Nutrient Profiling Model, NPM), and environmental quality (captured by the Environmental Footprint, EF, score). The panel structure allows us to control for both observable and unobservable heterogeneity, increasing the robustness of our findings.

Our results reveal a deterioration in the nutritional quality of food consumed over the observed period, particularly driven by an increasing trend in the content of sodium. At the same time, the overall environmental footprint of food consumption remained relatively stable, although households with higher calorie intake tend to have greater associated CO₂ emissions, suggesting that nutritionally poorer diets may also be more harmful to the environment.

The econometric analysis further highlights disparities in food consumption patterns across demographic and socioeconomic lines. Older households, well-off individuals, and families with young children tend to purchase healthier foods, reflected in lower NPM scores. In contrast, obesity and low-income households are strongly associated with poorer nutritional quality, independent of food quantity. Lastly, higher prices for healthy or eco-friendly foods correlate with worse dietary and environmental outcomes, underlining the importance of affordability.

By exploring both consumption behavior and its nutritional and ecological consequences, this report contributes to the growing literature on sustainable diets. Its findings offer valuable insights for public policy aimed at improving health and mitigating environmental damage regarding food consumption.

2 Data Construction

Datasets

Within the objective of analyzing the evolution of food consumption and its quality, we constructed a varying database of food consumption for a representative sample of households. To accomplish this, it is imperative to link consumption with nutritional information and environmental impact. Align

with this purpose, we use five datasets: the Kantar WorldPanel dataset (2002–2019), which records at-home food purchases by a representative panel of French households; the CLASSFOOD food classification system; the CIQUAL database, which provides nutritional information of food products; the Agribalyse dataset, which includes indicators that measure the environmental implication of food products; and the INCA2 Recipes database, which offers detailed ingredient compositions for processed foods.

Kantar WorldPanel

The Kantar WorldPanel homescan dataset encompasses all at-home food purchases recorded by a representative sample of French households. This dataset includes comprehensive information about households (such as their region of residence, income, and socio-economic status), and as well as details about household members (such as their socio-professional category, education level, age, gender, height, and weight). In addition, it provides detailed data on purchases, covering the place of purchase, brand, price, quantity, and various characteristics of the product.

The dataset also includes information on the representativeness of households relative to the French population. Specifically, Kantar WorldPanel assigns annual weights to households¹ that report purchases during at least ten four-week periods out of the thirteen periods in a year. These weights ensure that the sample remains representative of the French population while also accounting for periods of inactivity, where the household does not declare any purchase.

CLASSFOOD

CLASSFOOD is a comprehensive food nomenclature grounded in the French food supply and consumption. Food categories are systematically designed based on nutritional, environmental, and processing characteristics (Spiteri et al., 2023). This classification supports in-depth analysis of food sustainability while considering consumption patterns within the French population, including substitutability between food products.

As a hierarchical framework, foodstuffs are categorized across varying levels of detail, enabling analysis of diets either as a whole or within specific categories. At the first level, food products are grouped into 12 broad categories.² The second level splits the diet in 54 categories. The third and fourth levels contain 153 and 194 categories, respectively. Finally, the fifth level, the most detailed one, distinguish food products into 224 categories.

¹This weight information is available for only a subset of households.

²These 12 main categories are: Cereals products, Fruits and vegetables, Meat, fish, & eggs, Dairy products, Sweet products, Oils & fats, Drinks, Ready-made meals, Appetizers, Sauces & condiments, Plant-based proteins, and Other products.

CIQUAL

The CIQUAL database provides detailed macronutrient and micronutrient values for over 3,185 food and drink products representative of consumption in France. Macronutrients include carbohydrates, dietary fiber, fats, and proteins, while micronutrients encompass various vitamins and minerals. This publicly accessible database is managed by the Centre d’information sur la qualité des aliments (Ciqual), a part of the Agence nationale de sécurité sanitaire de l’alimentation, de l’environnement et du travail (Anses), a French governmental agency. We use the 2020 version of this database.

Agribalyse

Agribalyse is a comprehensive farm-to-fork Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) database that provides data on the environmental impacts of more than 2,516 French agricultural and food products. The data are derived using the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) method, which evaluates environmental impact indicators across all stages of production, distribution, and consumption. The database includes various indicators, such as the climate change indicator, land use, eutrophication, depletion, acidification and the Environmental Footprint (EF) score, which aggregates these indicators into a single score reflecting the environmental impact for different products. Agribalyse is linked to the CIQUAL database through a common identification key for food products, facilitating comprehensive analyses. We also use the 2020 version of this dataset.

INCA2 Recipes

The INCA2 recipe database was created in 2006-2007 in the context of the French national survey of individual food intakes INCA2. It uses a nomenclature of 1280 food products. Among them, 654 food products are raw or minimally processed food products, 626 are processed food products (ready meals...) that can be decomposed into ingredients. This decomposition is very precise as the database considers 760 ingredients and estimate a percentage of each of them. This database is also related to the CIQUAL database as it mentions for each product the related identification key of CIQUAL.³

Data Generating Process

To analyze the evolution of food consumption, it is necessary to generate a household panel dataset detailing yearly at-home food consumption by French households. Figure 1 illustrates the interrelation of the data. First, the databases —CIQUAL and Agribalyse— are linked using a common identifier corresponding to the identification of the products. Food products are then assigned to

³As we only use a unique database for recipes, we assume that the recipes of products offered on the market is constant over time.

one of the 224 food categories in the CLASSFOOD classification, and simple averages are calculated for each nutritional and environmental information.

Figure 1: Relationships between databases

Second, all food purchases in the Kantar Worldpanel database are classified using the CLASSFOOD system. This classification serves as the new identification key, enabling the integration of all four databases. Finally, quantities and expenditures can be aggregated for each household and year. For quantities, it is necessary to address discrepancies in the measurement units of purchased products. Kantar records quantities based on the units used during sale: Liquid products are measured in liters or milliliters, solid products in kilograms or grams, and some items (e.g., salads, avocados) are sold per unit. To standardize these measurements, the dataset converts all products into kilograms, providing an equivalent weight.

To compare food consumption across households, recording all food purchases is essential. Nonetheless, Kantar does not collect all purchases from every household consistently over time. From 2008 to 2019, all households declares all food products, yet, before 2008 the situation is more complex, where we have three panels: GC (barcode purchases), VP (meat and fish without barcodes), and FL (fruits and vegetables without barcodes). Among the 224 food categories, 27 contains both products with and without barcode, 3 are only collected by GC-FL and 24 by GC-VP. Consider a food category that contains products with a bar code, GC, and fruits and vegetables without a barcode, FL. This food category is therefore GC-FL and we observe full purchase quantities and expenses for households that belong to the GC-FL panel. For households belonging to the GC-VP panel, we only observe their purchase quantities and expenses for products with a barcode (GC), but not their purchases for fruits and vegetables without a barcode (FL). We therefore need to estimate FL for the GC-VP households. The problem is similar for the food categories that contain products with a bar code, GC, and meat and fish without a code bar, VP. We need to estimate VP for the GC-FL

households. To overcome this missing data⁴ problem of some food categories for some households, we implement a procedure of imputation at the household level as in (Bonnet et al., 2014). The objective is to perform a Propensity Score Matching (PSM), which estimates quantities and expenditures for unobserved food categories (GC-FL or GC-VP) based on observed data.

To compare different socio-demographic populations we created groups based on key metrics. For instance, regarding the age, we created 4 groups that are based on the age of the panelist⁵ of each household. Based on the World Health Organization’s (WHO) ranges that categorizes the Body Mass Index (BMI), we compared and analyzed the obesity status⁶ throughout 3 groups: Normal (BMI less than 25 kg/m²), Overweight (BMI between 25 and 30 kg/m²), and Obese (BMI more than 30 kg/m²). To exhibit how having a child of less than 6 years old can affect dietary decisions, we created a dummy variable that determines if there is one child or more in the household.

Additionally, we classify households according to their socio-economic status, considering income and household size. The classification consists of four groups: Well-off, Upper-middle, Lower-middle, and Modeste. Another important factor is inactivity, which accounts for whether at least one person in the household is retired or unemployed. Moreover, to examine regional variations, we segment households into eight geographic regions based on the Kantar classification: Paris, East, North, West, Center West, Center East, South East, and South West. Lastly, education level is another key variable, as it can influence nutritional awareness and food selection. We categorize panelists into four groups: those with a short education (Formation Courte), those who completed a Baccalauréate, individuals with two years of higher education (Bac+2), and those with more than two years of higher education (> Bac+2).

To allow a direct comparison of households of different sizes and compositions, we are using the concept of Adult Male Equivalents (AME) (FAO/WHO, 2004). The AMEs method provides coefficients for each household member for an adult male equivalent food consumption that depends on age and gender. Hence, values are given per person (per capita), taking the AME as the reference, even though these correspond to household averages. These weights ensure a comparison that accounts for the heterogeneity within households.

3 Methodology

In this section we present the methodology to construct the key variables used in this report. Variables are grouped in three domains: purchase variables, including quantities, expenditures, prices, and price indices; nutritional quality variables, including the Nutrient Profile Method score (NPM)

⁴It has to be noted that the missing information is not systematically related to some household consumption behavior and concerns a small percentage of household consumption on average.

⁵Panelist refers to the person in charge of the food purchases.

⁶The categorization of this group is based on the actual BMI from the panelist.

and its components; and environmental impact variables, including Environmental footprint Score (EF) and its main components.

3.1 Purchase Variables

Let H_t be the number of households in year t , T the total number of periods (years), and K the number of food categories.

Quantity

Let q_{htk} be the quantity of food purchases at home per capita male equivalent of household h in year t for each food category k . The household h average daily food consumption per capita male equivalent is

$$Q_{htk} = \frac{q_{htk}}{Nd_t} \quad (1)$$

where Nd_t is the number of days in year t .

Aggregating across food categories and households, and weighting by households representativeness in year t , W_{ht} , \bar{Q}_t gives the yearly average quantity consumed at home, per capita male equivalent:

$$\bar{Q}_t = \frac{\sum_{h=1}^{H_t} \sum_{k=1}^K Q_{htk} \cdot W_{ht}}{\sum_{h=1}^{H_t} W_{ht}} \quad (2)$$

Expenditures

Analogously to quantities, we compute for household h the average daily at-home food expenditures per food category k in year t , per capita adult male equivalent:

$$E_{htk} = \frac{e_{htk}}{Nd_t} \quad (3)$$

where e_{htk} is annual expenditures of household h in year t for food category k , per capita male equivalent. And aggregating, early average at home food expenditures, per capita male equivalent:

$$\bar{E}_t = \frac{\sum_{h=1}^{H_t} \sum_{k=1}^K E_{htk} \cdot W_{ht}}{\sum_{h=1}^{H_t} W_{ht}} \quad (4)$$

We use deflate expenditures and prices to 2002 prices by the Consumer Price Index from the Institut National de la Statistique et des Études Économiques (INSEE) (2024).

Price

We recover average annual price per kilogram of food from expenditures and quantities purchased. Price per food category k in year t is thus

$$P_{tk} = \frac{\sum_{h=1}^{H_t} E_{htk}}{\sum_{h=1}^{H_t} Q_{htk}} \quad (5)$$

and general food price in t is

$$P_t = \frac{\sum_{h=1}^{H_t} \sum_{k=1}^K E_{htk}}{\sum_{h=1}^{H_t} \sum_{k=1}^K Q_{htk}} \quad (6)$$

Price Index

We construct a price index to track the evolution of prices of food and food categories over time. The general price of food in year t , Π_t , is a weighted sum of all food categories' prices :

$$\Pi_t = \sum_{k=1}^K S_{tk} P_{tk} \quad (7)$$

where P_{tk} is given by (5) and S_k is the average share of food category k in total food home consumption over the period 2002-2019. The share S_k can be measured either in terms of quantities or expenditures. A **quantity-based share** is calculated as the percentage of category k in total food purchased in kg:

$$SQ_k = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{h=1}^{H_t} Q_{htk}}{\sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{h=1}^{H_t} \sum_{k=1}^K Q_{htk}} \quad (8)$$

Alternatively, an **expenditure-based share** can be used:

$$SQ_k = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{h=1}^{H_t} E_{htk}}{\sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{h=1}^{H_t} \sum_{k=1}^K E_{htk}} \quad (9)$$

A general food price index measures price evolution with respect to the base year 2002 weighting

food categories either by their share of quantities or expenditures. It is thus given by

$$\text{Index}_t = \sum_{k=1}^K S_k \left(\frac{P_{tk}}{P_{2002,k}} \right) \times 100 \quad (10)$$

where $P_{2002,k}$ corresponds to the price of category k in the base year 2002 and $S_k = \{SQ_k, SE_k\}$.

3.2 NPM Score and its components

We use the UK Ofcom Nutrient Profiling Model (NPM) as a proxy of food nutritional quality (Rayner and Scarborough, 2009). The NPM balances both unhealthy and healthy nutrients per 100g of food. First, points are assigned to unhealthy nutrients, referred to as "A" points. These include energy, saturated fat, total sugar, and sodium, with scores ranging from 0 to 10 for each nutrient. Table 1 specifies A points attributed per 100g of food.

Points	Energy (kJ)	Sat Fat (g)	Total Sugar (g)	Sodium (mg)
0	≤ 335	≤ 1	≤ 4.5	≤ 90
1	> 335	> 1	> 4.5	> 90
2	> 670	> 2	> 9	> 180
3	> 1005	> 3	> 13.5	> 270
4	> 1340	> 4	> 18	> 360
5	> 1675	> 5	> 22.5	> 450
6	> 2010	> 6	> 27	> 540
7	> 2345	> 7	> 31	> 630
8	> 2680	> 8	> 36	> 720
9	> 3015	> 9	> 40	> 810
10	> 3350	> 10	> 45	> 900

Table 1: NPM unhealthy component, "A" Points per 100g of food

Then, points are awarded to healthy nutrients, referred to as "C" points. These include the percentage of fruits, vegetables, and nuts, fiber, and protein content. See table Table 2 for the specific thresholds for points attributed.⁷

⁷Potatoes and other starchy vegetables do not count as vegetables. Furthermore, the weight of dried fruit and vegetables is counted double, as smaller amounts of dried fruits and vegetables are equivalent to one standard portion of fresh fruit or vegetables. Also fibre is measured as Non Starch Polysaccharides (NSP) or as the Association of Official Analytical Chemists (AOAC). Please see the Nutrient Profiling Technical Guidance (Department of Health, 2011) for further specifications and details.

Points	Fruit & Veg (%)	NSP Fibre (g)	or AOAC Fibre (g)	Protein (g)
0	≤ 40	≤ 0.7	≤ 0.9	≤ 1.6
1	> 40	> 0.7	> 0.9	> 1.6
2	> 60	> 1.4	> 1.9	> 3.2
3	-	> 2.1	> 2.8	> 4.8
4	-	> 2.8	> 3.7	> 6.4
5	> 80	> 3.5	> 4.7	> 8.0

Table 2: NPM healthy component, "C" Points per 100g of food

The NPM score for a food product is then calculated as the difference between the total "A" points and the total "C" points:

$$NPM = \text{Total 'A' Points} - \text{Total 'C' Points} \quad (11)$$

If the total "A" points are less than 11, all "C" points are used. If the total "A" points are 11 or more, the use of "C" points depends on the score for fruit, vegetables, and nuts: all "C" points are used if the score for fruit, vegetables, and nuts is 5 or higher; otherwise, only fibre and fruits, vegetables and nuts points are used.

A food product is considered healthy if the NPM score is lower than 4. For drinks the cut-off value is 1. So following Equation 11, we can define "healthy" and "unhealthy" zones based on the the total "A" points and "C" points as we can see in Figure 2.

Figure 2: "Healthy" and "Unhealthy" zones based in the intersection between A points and C points

We calculate the NPM score for each of the 224 food categories of the ClasSfood classification (see Table 11 in the Annex).⁸ We also compute the NPM score for the household at-home food consumption, weighting the 224 food categories by the quantity of each food category consumed. We calculate these aggregates for food and drinks separately as the healthy thresholds differ. So, the average NPM of household h in time t of food consumption at home is

$$NPM_{ht} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^K (NPM_k \cdot Q_{htk})}{\sum_{k=1}^K Q_{htk}} \quad (12)$$

Aggregating across households and accounting for their representativeness W_{ht} gives, the population average NPM in time t

$$\overline{NPM}_t = \frac{\sum_{h=1}^{H_t} (NPM_{ht} \cdot W_{ht})}{\sum_{h=1}^{H_t} W_{ht}} \quad (13)$$

Besides a measure for general nutritional quality, we are also interested in tracking some specific NPM components, such as those in Table 1. For those NPM components (c) we compute the average content per 100g of food consumed at home by each household considering all categories purchased (daily per capita male equivalent).

$$C_{htc} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^K (C_{kc} \cdot Q_{htk})}{\sum_{k=1}^K Q_{htk}} \quad (14)$$

where C_{kc} is the average content of the component c per 100g of food in category k .

Lastly, the average daily at-home intake of the NPM component c for a household in a given year (IC_{htc}) is approximated by adding component c_k of category k (per 100g) over average daily quantities of food categories purchased (in kg):

$$IC_{htc} = \sum_{k=1}^K (10 \cdot c_k \cdot Q_{htk}) \quad (15)$$

⁸The values of the components for the "A" points and "C" points come from CIQUAL, except for the fruit, vegetables, and nuts percentage (%) which comes mostly from the INCA2 Recipes database.

3.3 Environmental Footprint Score and its components

The Environmental Footprint (EF) score is a method recommended by the European Commission to aggregate environmental impact indicators into a single score. By integrating various impact categories, such as greenhouse gas emissions, land use, water consumption, air pollution, and resource depletion, the EF score offers insights into which products contribute more to environmental degradation. It enables comparisons across different consumption patterns and production processes. In the context of this analysis, the EF score is used to assess the environmental sustainability of food consumption.

We compute the EF score, EF_k , for the 224 ClasSfood categories by merging ClasSfood to Agribalyse. To compute the household EF score for the generality of its at-home food purchases, we weighted each food category by its share of total food purchased (in kg). Household h EF score in year t is given by:

$$EF_{ht} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^K (EF_k \cdot Q_{htk})}{\sum_{k=1}^K Q_{htk}} \quad (16)$$

Aggregating across households gives the average EF scores in year t :

$$\overline{EF}_t = \frac{\sum_{h=1}^{H_t} (EF_{ht} \cdot W_{ht})}{\sum_{h=1}^{H_t} W_{ht}} \quad (17)$$

where we account for the household's representativeness W_{ht} .

As for the nutritional dimension, also here we are interested to have a closer look at specific environmental factors. The average environmental indicator of a component c per 1 kilogram of food for a household h in a specific year t (EI_{htc}) is expressed using the following formula:

$$EI_{htc} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^K (EI_k \cdot Q_{htk})}{\sum_{k=1}^K Q_{htk}} \quad (18)$$

Additionally, we can think of the EF of daily intakes for a household in a specific year. Let IEI_{htc} be calculated as the sum of the products of the average content of a component per 100 grams EI_k

and the daily at-home quantity intake Q_{htk} , expressed as:

$$IEI_{htc} = \sum_{k=1}^K (10 \cdot EI_k \cdot Q_{htk}) \quad (19)$$

3.4 Construction of the Relative Price Index

Healthy/Unhealthy Price Index

This section details the methodology used to construct the Relative Price Index (RPI) between healthy and unhealthy food products that is used in the econometric analysis. The construction follows a series of steps to compute price indices separately for healthy and unhealthy food categories before obtaining their relative measure. A food category is considered healthy if its Nutrient Profile Model (NPM) score is less than 4 for solid food items and less than 1 for drinks. Otherwise, it is classified as unhealthy (Rayner and Scarborough, 2009).

For a given year t and a geographical region (department) d , the total deflated expenditure on healthy food products for category k is computed as:

$$TE_{tdk}^{\text{He}^+} = \sum_{h=1}^{H_t} \text{EXP}_{htdk}^{\text{He}^+} \quad (20)$$

where $\text{EXP}_{htdk}^{\text{He}^+}$ represents the deflated expenditure of household h on healthy food items in category k .

Similarly, the total quantity purchased of healthy food is given by:

$$TQ_{tdk}^{\text{He}^+} = \sum_{h=1}^{H_t} \text{QU}_{htdk}^{\text{He}^+} \quad (21)$$

where $\text{QU}_{htdk}^{\text{He}^+}$ denotes the quantity consumed of household h on healthy food items in category k .

The average price for healthy food, $P_{tdk}^{\text{He}^+}$, is then computed as:

$$P_{tdk}^{\text{He}^+} = \frac{TE_{tdk}^{\text{He}^+}}{TQ_{tdk}^{\text{He}^+}} \quad (22)$$

A similar procedure is followed for unhealthy food products (He^-):

$$P_{tdk}^{\text{He}^-} = \frac{TE_{tdk}^{\text{He}^-}}{TQ_{tdk}^{\text{He}^-}} \quad (23)$$

For each household h , we compute the weight for each food category k as:

$$w_{hk}^{\text{He}^+} = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T Q_{hk}^{\text{He}^+}}{T \sum_{k=1}^K Q_h^{\text{He}^+}}, \quad w_{hk}^{\text{He}^-} = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T Q_{hk}^{\text{He}^-}}{T \sum_{k=1}^K Q_h^{\text{He}^-}} \quad (24)$$

The household-level food price indices for healthy and unhealthy food products are computed as:

$$\text{FPI}_{ht}^{\text{He}^+} = \sum_k P_{tdk}^{\text{He}^+} \cdot w_{hk}^{\text{He}^+} \quad (25)$$

$$\text{FPI}_{ht}^{\text{He}^-} = \sum_k P_{tdk}^{\text{He}^-} \cdot w_{hk}^{\text{He}^-} \quad (26)$$

The relative price index (RPI) for household h in year t is defined as the logarithm of the ratio of the food price indices:

$$\text{RPI}_{ht} = \ln \left(\frac{\text{FPI}_{ht}^{\text{He}^+}}{\text{FPI}_{ht}^{\text{He}^-}} \right) \quad (27)$$

To obtain a standardized measure, we compute the mean of RPI_{ht} across households and define the deviation from this mean as:

$$\widehat{\text{RPI}}_{ht} = \text{RPI}_{ht} - \overline{\text{RPI}}_{ht} \quad (28)$$

where $\overline{\text{RPI}}_{ht}$ represents the average relative price index for year t , expressed as:

$$\overline{\text{RPI}}_{ht} = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \text{RPI}_{ht} \quad (29)$$

Eco-Friendly/Non Eco-Friendly Price Index

A food category is considered eco-friendly if its Environmental Footprint (EF) score is less than 0.41. Otherwise, it is classified as non eco-friendly. This threshold was chosen based on an extrapolation of the healthiness cut-off from the NPM Score, where a value of 4 corresponds to the 57th percentile, matching the percentile rank of 0.41 in the EF score distribution.

For a given year t and a geographical region (department) d , the total deflated expenditure on

eco-friendly food products for category k is calculated as:

$$TE_{tdk}^{\text{En}^+} = \sum_{h=1}^{H_t} \text{EXP}_{htdk}^{\text{En}^+} \quad (30)$$

where $\text{EXP}_{htdk}^{\text{En}^+}$ corresponds to the deflated expenditure of household h on eco-friendly food items within category k .

Likewise, the total quantity purchased of eco-friendly food for product k is given by:

$$TQ_{tdk}^{\text{En}^+} = \sum_{h=1}^{H_t} \text{QU}_{htdk}^{\text{En}^+} \quad (31)$$

where $TQ_{tdk}^{\text{En}^+}$ denotes the total quantity of eco-friendly food purchased.

The average price for eco-friendly food, $P_{tdk}^{\text{En}^+}$, is computed as:

$$P_{tdk}^{\text{En}^+} = \frac{TE_{tdk}^{\text{En}^+}}{TQ_{tdk}^{\text{En}^+}} \quad (32)$$

A similar computation is performed for non eco-friendly food products (En^-):

$$P_{tdk}^{\text{En}^-} = \frac{TE_{tdk}^{\text{En}^-}}{TQ_{tdk}^{\text{En}^-}} \quad (33)$$

For each household h , we determine the weight for each food category k as:

$$w_{hk}^{\text{En}^+} = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T Q_{hk}^{\text{En}^+}}{\sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{k=1}^K Q_h^{\text{En}^+}}, \quad w_{hk}^{\text{En}^-} = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^T Q_{hk}^{\text{En}^-}}{\sum_{t=1}^T \sum_{k=1}^K Q_h^{\text{En}^-}} \quad (34)$$

The household-level food price indices for eco-friendly and non eco-friendly food products are computed as:

$$\text{FPI}_{ht}^{\text{En}^+} = \sum_k P_{tdk}^{\text{En}^+} \cdot w_{hk}^{\text{En}^+}, \quad (35)$$

$$\text{FPI}_{ht}^{\text{En}^-} = \sum_k P_{tdk}^{\text{En}^-} \cdot w_{hk}^{\text{En}^-} \quad (36)$$

The relative price index (RPI) for household h in year t is defined as the logarithm of the ratio of

the food price indices:

$$\text{RPI}_{ht} = \ln \left(\frac{\text{FPI}_{ht}^{\text{En}^+}}{\text{FPI}_{ht}^{\text{En}^-}} \right) \quad (37)$$

To obtain a standardized measure, we compute the mean of RPI_{ht} across households and define the deviation from this mean as:

$$\widehat{\text{RPI}}_{ht} = \text{RPI}_{ht} - \overline{\text{RPI}}_{ht} \quad (38)$$

where $\overline{\text{RPI}}_{ht}$ represents the average relative price index for year t .

$$\overline{\text{RPI}}_{ht} = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \text{RPI}_{ht} \quad (39)$$

4 Evolution of Food purchases

4.1 General overview

In this section, we will focus on the general evolution across time of the main purchase metrics (quantity, expenditures and price). First, it is important to underscore the chosen dimensions to these main variables. For the quantity, we are considering all the consumption in the same unit of measurement (kilograms). The expenditures and prices are expressed in Euros. For quantities and expenditures, we are calculating the household's average at-home consumption of food per day by Adult Male Equivalent (AME).⁹ Deflated expenditures and prices are calculated using 2002 as the base year, based on the Consumer Price Index (Indice des Prix à la Consommation, IPC) provided by the Institut National de la Statistique et des Études Économiques (INSEE).

Figure 3 shows the main purchase variables evolution over the time period. In France the average daily per capita quantity consumption is between 1.5 and 1.7 kilogram per day, with a relatively stable time evolution. Regarding the deflated expenditures, we can observe that a French individual spends on average between 5 and 6 euros for food per day for home-food consumption. Between 2002 and 2019, deflated expenditures showed a relatively steady increase, rising from approximately 5 euros in 2002 to over 6 euros in 2019—a growth of 20%.

Figure 3: Quantity, expenditures and price evolution of at-home food consumption
Note: Household's average values in per capita male equivalent. Price and expenditures deflated to 2002 prices.

We can find a similar increasing trend in the deflated price per kilogram of food computed as in equation (6). This can be explained partially by the constant augmentation of food prices. In

⁹Throughout the graphical analysis, the expressions "by individual" or "per capita" hold within the Adult Male Equivalence reference.

Figure 4, we can observe the evolution of the different methods of the price indexes and its comparison with the Food Price Index (FPI) provided by the *Institut National des Statistiques et des Etudes Economiques* (INSEE).¹⁰

Figure 4: INSEE and Kantar general Food Price Indexes comparison
 Note: 2003 as the base year for the Indices calculation.

We perceive a similar trend shared by the methods implemented in section 3 for the food price index calculation, with the FPI from INSEE. From the 3 homologous indexes we have seen an approximately 25% increase from 2002 to 2019.

Figure 5 compares the trends in quantity, expenditures, and price evolution indices from 2002 to 2019, with 2002 as the base year. By 2019, the quantity index shows minimal growth, with only a 10% increase compared to 2002, indicating relatively stable consumption levels. In contrast, the deflated expenditures and deflated price have risen by approximately 20% and 10%, respectively, reflecting modest real increases in prices and spending. When examining the nominal values, the changes are more pronounced. The nominal price has increased by around 30%, and nominal expenditures by around 50%, highlighting the impact of inflation over the period.

¹⁰The Food Price Indices from INSEE can be found at: <https://www.insee.fr/en/statistiques/series/102342213>

Figure 5: Quantity, Expenditures and Prices Index of at-home food consumption Comparison (base 2002)

Note: Household’s average values in per capita male equivalent. 2002 used as the base year.

4.2 Evolution of Food purchases by food categories

We analyze the consumption metrics with a focus on 12 primary food categories, corresponding to the first level of the ClasSFood classification, and we additionally distinguish between the type of meats consumed, see Table 3. Fruits & Vegetables dominate in terms of quantity consumed (28.3%), signifying their central role in dietary habits. Despite their large share in quantity, they account for only 16.0% of expenditures, indicating a lower price per kilogram (€1.89). This highlights their cost-efficiency and accessibility in comparison to other food categories.

Conversely, Meat, Fish, & Eggs hold the highest percentage of expenditures (30.1%), despite contributing only 12.5% to the total quantity consumed. This discrepancy arises due to their significantly higher price per kilogram (€8.09), underscoring the economic impact of protein-rich foods on household budgets. Dairy Products, constituting 18.4% of total quantity consumed, remain a staple category, contributing 13.0% to expenditures with a moderate price of €2.36 per kilogram. Drinks¹¹ (19.7%) also account for a substantial share of consumption, aligning closely with their expenditure share (14.7%), and priced at €2.50 per kilogram. In contrast, Sweet Products, though only 6.6% of total quantity, represent 10.0% of expenditures, highlighting their relatively higher price per kilogram (€5.10). Similarly, Ready-made Meals and Appetizers have elevated costs per kilogram (€5.03 and €7.19, respectively), reflecting the premium on convenience foods.

¹¹It is important to note that all analyses and graphical representations presented in this work exclude water intake. Thus, water products (still and sparkling) were removed from the purchase and consumption data. This exclusion is justified by water’s disproportionately large volume compared to other products and its low nutritional significance.

Food Classification	Quantity (%)	Expenditures (%)	Price per kg (in €)
Cereal Products	4.2%	2.8%	2.22
Fruits & Vegetables	28.3%	16.0%	1.89
Meat, Fish & Eggs	12.5%	30.1%	8.09
Dairy Products	18.4%	13.0%	2.36
Sweet Products	6.6%	10.0%	5.10
Oils & Fats	2.7%	3.0%	3.66
Drinks	19.7%	14.7%	2.50
Ready-made meals	3.8%	5.7%	5.03
Appetizers	0.6%	1.3%	7.19
Sauces	1.9%	1.7%	3.13
Plant Protein	0.6%	0.5%	2.61
Other Products	0.8%	1.2%	5.10

Table 3: Food categories and associated consumption metrics

Note: Quantity and expenditures are given in the relative proportion or weight of each food category. Prices are expressed in euros and are deflated by 2002 prices.

Figure 6 shows the quantities consumed across the 12 main food categories ((in %) of kg). Fruits & Vegetables exhibit the highest median consumption, with a considerable spread, indicating varying intake levels among individuals. Meat, Fish & Eggs and Dairy also show notable median values, reflecting their significance in diets. Drinks display a wide interquartile range, suggesting a high variation in consumption patterns. Ready-made meals, while consumed in lower absolute quantities, have a broad spread, indicating differing dietary preferences. Sweet Products and Fats show moderate variability, likely due to discretionary consumption. Appetizers, Sauces & Condiments, Plant-based Proteins, and Other Products have the lowest median and interquartile range, signifying minimal consumption.

Figure 6: Distribution of the household's relative quantity consumed (%) by Food Classification
Note: Household's average values in per capita male equivalent.

It is also crucial to exhibit the time evolution of the purchase and consumption variables by the main food classifications. In Figure 7 and Figure 8 we can observe the evolution of the quantity, deflated expenditures and deflated prices throughout the years for the main food classifications. For Cereal Products, both quantity consumed and deflated expenditures show a similar trend, with a notable increase of over 40% from 2002 to 2019. In contrast, the deflated price per kilogram of cereal products has remained relatively stable, fluctuating only slightly around the base index of 100. This indicates that the growth in expenditures is primarily driven by increased consumption rather than rising prices. Similarly, Fruits and Vegetables show a significant upward trend in both quantity consumed and deflated expenditures, with increases of approximately 30% to 40%, and with an increasing deflated price by 10% over the period.

From 2002 to approximately 2012, there was a notable increase in both quantity consumed and total expenditures for Meat, fish & eggs, indicating growing consumption trends. However, after reaching a peak around 2012, both quantity and expenditures began to decline steadily. This decline suggests a reduction in overall demand or shifts in consumption patterns. Interestingly, the deflated price index remained relatively stable throughout the observed period. Conversely, the price index for the Dairy category, exhibited a steady and significant increase throughout the period, with a constant declining in the quantity consumed over the period. In contrast, expenditures on dairy remained relatively stable.

For the Sweet products we can observe a moderate increase of the quantity consumed, reflecting a consistent upward trend. Expenditures, however, grew at a faster pace, particularly after 2011 with a global increase of 30%. The price index remained relatively stable between 2002 and 2015, but then after the decrease in the quantity and the increase in the expenditures, prices began to rise steadily.

Over the period, the quantity consumed and expenditures of Ready-made meals followed a similar upward trend (+ 55% global increase from 2002 to 2019), particularly between 2004 and 2012, where both saw a notable increase. After 2012, the growth rate slowed, and the gap between quantity and expenditures decreased substantially. In contrast, the price remained relatively stable throughout the period. For Appetizers, the quantity consumed and expenditures show a large increase in quantities (around 40% from 2002 to 2019). Finally, for the plant-based proteins, there have been gradual increases in quantity consumed and expenditures per capita, particularly from 2011. Notably, the price index has remained below 100, indicating relatively stable or declining prices compared to the base year.

Figure 7: Time evolution of the Quantity, Expenditures, and Prices by Food Classification: Cereals Products, Fruits & Vegetables, Meat, Fish & Eggs, and Dairy products

Note: Household's average values in per capita male equivalent. Price and expenditures deflated to 2002 prices.

Figure 8: Time evolution of the Quantity, Expenditures, and Prices by Food Classification: Sweet Products, Ready-made meals, Appetizers, and Plant-based proteins

Note: Household's average values in per capita male equivalent. Price and expenditures deflated to 2002 prices.

Table 4 highlights variations in quantity share, expenditures, and price per kg across different meat categories. Pork represents the largest share of consumption (31.5%) and expenditures (28.6%), reflecting its affordability (€7.95/kg) compared to other meats like lamb & goat (€11.03/kg) and fresh seafood (€10.63/kg). Fresh seafood, despite a lower quantity share (14.3%), has the second-highest expenditure (17.4%), indicating a higher price influence. Chicken, a widely consumed option (10.6%), remains one of the most affordable meats (€5.87/kg), aligning with its moderate expenditure share (7.1%). Beef also holds a significant presence in both consumption (12.9%) and spending (14.7%), with an average price of €10.01/kg. Cooked meats and seafood exhibit lower consumption shares but still maintain notable expenditures, likely due to added processing costs.

Meat Categories	Quantity (%)	Expenditures (%)	Price per kg (in €)
Beef	12.9%	14.7%	10.01
Veal	3.6%	5.5%	13.29
Lamb & Goat	3.3%	4.1%	11.03
Chicken	10.6%	7.1%	5.87
Turkey	3.1%	2.5%	7.03
Other Poultry	5.1%	6.0%	10.24
Pork	31.5%	28.6%	7.95
Other Meats	1.0%	1.4%	13.03
Mixed Meats	1.4%	1.1%	7.14
Cooked Meats	7.0%	6.2%	7.82
Fresh Seafood	14.3%	17.4%	10.63
Cooked Seafood	6.3%	5.3%	7.38

Table 4: Meat categories and main consumption associated variables

Note: Expenditures and Prices are deflated by 2002 prices. Other meats includes deer, roe deer, wild boar, kangaroo, and offal. Mixed meats include pork and beef skewers, pâté made with several meats, or mixed sausages. Other poultry includes rabbit, duck, guinea fowl, hare, goose, quail, and ostrich.

In Figure 9 we observe the consumption evolution of red meat, pork, poultry, and processed meats in terms of quantity, deflated expenditures, and deflated price.¹² Red meat shows a steady decline in consumption over time, with expenditures following a similar trend, while prices shows moderate increases, reflecting shifting dietary preferences. Pork, as a significant category, shows a clear pattern of growth until it peaks in 2012, after which it begins to decline. Similarly, deflated expenditures on pork increase until 2012, followed by a gradual decrease. Interestingly, the price of pork remains relatively stable throughout most of the period, however, in the last years, a notable upward trend in prices emerges, due to rising expenditures and declining quantities.

Similar to pork, poultry consumption rises until 2012, then declines steadily, with expenditures mirroring this trend, although the magnitude in the growth of expenditures is considerably higher than the quantity consumed, making the deflated price per kilogram of poultry to have a positive

¹²Red meat includes beef, veal, lamb and goat. Poultry includes chicken, turkey and other poultry.

steady growth. Finally, for the consumption evolution of processed meat, both quantity and deflated expenditures display a consistent upward trajectory throughout the entire period, growing at a similar rate. This parallel growth is consistent with the stability of processed meat prices over time. Notably, the percentage change for both quantity and expenditures is remarkable, with an increase of more than 80% in 2019 compared to the baseline in 2002.

Figure 9: Time evolution of the Quantity, Expenditures, and Prices by Types of Meat: Red meat, Poultry, Pork and Processed Meats. Note: Household's average values in per capita male equivalent. Price and expenditures deflated to 2002 prices.

5 Evolution of nutritional quality of food purchases

5.1 General overview

The Nutrient Profiling Model (NPM) Score represents the average nutritional quality and healthfulness of 100 grams of food products. Figure 10 shows the evolution of the yearly household's average NPM Score of households' at-home food consumption. Over the years we can observe a general upward but moderate tendency of the NPM score, reflecting a detrimental nutritional quality in time. The interquartile range (Quartile 75) follows a similar moderate increasing trend, suggesting that the general shift towards lower nutritional quality is consistent across households. The 5th percentile remains relatively stable over the years, indicating that the healthiest food consumption patterns have not changed significantly. Interestingly, the 95th percentile exhibits a more pronounced increase, rising from around 5 in 2002 to over 6 in 2019, highlighting a worsening nutritional profile for the least healthy diets.

Figure 10: Average NPM Score by household per year with their 5%, 25%, 75%, and 95% percentiles

As stated in the methodology section, the score depends on specific nutrients and nutritional aspects. To understand the main drivers on the general healthiness of household's diets, we also analyse the evolution of the NPM components. In Figure 11 and Figure 12, we illustrate the time evolution of the "negative" or unhealthy nutrients and the "positive" or healthy nutrients, respectively. For every component or nutrient we display the yearly average content per 100g of food, the daily average intake and an index comparison between them to reflect the difference between the quality (content per 100g) and quantity aspect (daily intake). Regarding the energy we see an increase in calorie intake (+15%) from 2002 to 2019, driven both by higher consumption volumes in terms of the quantity (+10%) as we saw in Figure 5, and a rise in the average calorie content of products (+5%). Therefore, the growth in the average daily intake of calories shows a greater magnitude than the average

energy content. A similar pattern is observed for the other ‘unhealthy’ nutrients, with the effect being particularly pronounced for sodium, with an increase of more than 20% of the average sodium content of food diet and an increase of more than 35% of average sodium intake from 2002 to 2019 ¹³.

Regarding the evolution of the ‘healthy’ NPM components, the Fruits and Vegetables percentage plays the most significant role in determining the score, making its analysis highly relevant. Between 2002 and 2008, both metrics show an upward trend, followed by relative stagnation from 2009 to 2019. This trend may partially explain the turning point observed in 2010 for the NPM Score evolution, where the NPM Score began to increase significantly more than in prior years. The same trend, but to a much lesser extent, can be observed in the evolution of other "positive" nutrients, such as the protein and fiber consumption.

¹³The increase in dietary sodium content is not driven by a rise in the sodium levels within each of the 224 food categories, as these are assumed to remain constant over time. Rather, it reflects a composition effect or shifts in consumption patterns toward food categories that are higher in sodium.

Figure 11: Time evolution of the "negative" or less healthier components of the NPM Score in terms of the average content and daily intake of products consumed at home: Energy (kcal), Saturated Fats (g), Sugar (g), and Sodium (mg).

Note: The daily intake values are expressed in per capita male equivalent. The Index graphical representations is taking 2002 as the base year.

Figure 12: Time evolution of the "positive" or healthier components of the NPM Score in terms of the average content and daily intake of products consumed at home: Fruits & Vegetables (%), Fiber (g), and Proteins (g).

Note: The daily intake values are expressed in per capita male equivalent. The Index graphical representations is taking 2002 as the base year.

Figure 13 summarizes the evolution of the NPM Score evolution and the evolution for the seven components of the score in terms of their quality (content per 100g of food), by using an index variation.¹⁴ In the graphical representation we observe that the increasing trend after 2010 is mainly driven by a rise in sodium and, at a lower extent, a rise in saturated fat and energy, despite a substantial increase in fiber (+12%) and fruit and vegetables (+9%). Interestingly, we observe a stagnation and even a slight decrease (-2%) of the sugar content of food product purchased by French households.¹⁵

Figure 13: NPM Score and its components Index (Average content per 100 gr of products)
 Note: The Indices takes 2002 as the base year.

5.2 Evolution of nutritional quality by food categories

Figure 14 illustrates the distribution of the average households' Nutrient Profiling Model (NPM) score over the whole period (2002-2019) across the different main food categories in French households.¹⁶ The red dashed line represents the healthy/unhealthy threshold. Fruits & vegetables and plant-based proteins exhibit the lowest NPM scores, confirming their high nutritional value. In contrast, fats, sweet products, appetizers, and sauces have the highest median NPM scores, suggesting they are the least nutritious categories. Dairy, ready-made meals, and meat, fish & eggs show moderate scores, reflecting their mixed nutritional profiles depending on product types and processing levels.

Besides the variation across categories, the interquartile ranges and whiskers, highlights the heterogeneity in the NPM scores within food categories. Some categories, such as sweet products and dairy,

¹⁴The base year for constructing the indexes is 2002.

¹⁵It has to be noted that this evolution reflects the change in purchases among the 224 food categories, whereas the nutritional quality of food categories remains constant as we only use the 2020 CIQUAL database.

¹⁶From the 12 main food classifications we are excluding Drinks and Other Products as they contained extreme heterogeneous food products within the categories or classifications.

exhibit a wide range of nutritional quality, indicating significant variation in product composition. In contrast, categories like fruits & vegetables and plant-based proteins show tighter distributions, suggesting greater nutritional consistency.

Figure 14: Distribution of the Household's average NPM Score over the whole period (2002-2019) by the main food classifications

In Figure 15 we can observe the graphical representation of the relationship between healthy points (C points) and unhealthy points (A points) across different food categories, with each circle's size indicating the relative average quantity consumed per individual (Adult Male Equivalent). The colored dots in the center of each circle corresponds to the intersection of the average "A" points and "C" points of each classification. The black dashed line serves as a threshold, distinguishing foods that fall into the healthy or unhealthy zones based on the crossing of their A and C points. Categories positioned below the line, such as Fruits & Vegetables are classified as healthier options.

In contrast, categories above the line, like Sweet and Appetizers, are classified as unhealthier options. Additionally, larger circles, such as Fruits & Vegetables and Dairy, highlight their significant share in daily consumption. Unhealthy categories above the threshold, such as oils & fats, sweet products, sauces, and appetizers, correspond to relatively smaller circles, meaning that they represent a small part of the daily consumption in terms of the quantity.

Figure 15: Average A (Unhealthy) points vs C (Healthy) points across the main food classifications
 Note: Colored dots represents the average of the intersection between the "A" points and "C" points for each food classification. The sizes of the circles are based on the relative quantity (%) consumed per individual for each food classification.

To analyze the time evolution of the nutritional quality over the food categories, Figure 16 illustrates the average "A" points and "C" points from the beginning (2002–2004) and the end (2017–2019) of the time frame. Observing the transitions over time, a general trend emerges where many food categories have shifted towards higher C points, but also higher A points.

One of the most notable changes is seen in Fruits & Vegetables, which has increased in size and maintained its position well below the health threshold, reinforcing its role as a staple in a healthy diet. Similarly, Cereals have remained in the healthier zone, with a slight increase in C points. On the other hand, Dairy has reduced significantly in size, reflecting a decrease in consumption over the years, but its placement near the threshold suggests a decrease in nutritional quality. Meat, Fish & Eggs and Ready-made meals, while still close to the threshold, have shown slight shifts in both directions, suggesting little variability in their composition and consumption trends over time. We can observe a similar size of the circle that corresponds to the sweet products, meaning a stable relative consumption over the years, however the shift of the circle to the right is evident, which corresponds to the gain of more healthy or A points.

Figure 16: Average A (Unhealthy) points vs C (Healthy) points comparison between the periods 2002-2004 and 2017-2019 across the main food classifications

Note: Colored dots represents the average of the intersection between the "A" points and "C" points for each food classification. The sizes of the circles are based on the relative quantity (%) consumed per individual for each food classification.

Finally, Figure 17 compares the households with the lowest nutritional quality (those in the 90 percentile of the NPM score) and households with an average nutritional quality or that are located within the 10 percentile. We can evidently see the change in the sizes of some specific food categories, as the case with fruits & vegetables, where its consumption is considerably lower in the households within the 90 percentile, as expected. Conversely for the sweet products, there is a significant increase in its consumption. Lastly, regarding the "A" points and "C" points, there is a shift on the averages of the intersections, especially for the categories that are close to the threshold. Households with the worst nutritional quality (percentile 90) exhibit higher unhealthy or "A" points on average, shifting the intersection from the "healthy" to the "unhealthy" zone for the meat, fish & eggs, and dairy products.

Figure 17: Average A (Unhealthy) points vs C (Healthy) points comparison between the 10 % percentile and 90 % percentile of household’s NPM score across the main food classifications
 Note: Colored dots represents the average of the intersection between the "A" points and "C" points for each food classification. The sizes of the circles are based on the relative quantity (%) consumed per individual for each food classification.

6 Evolution of environmental footprint of food purchases

6.1 General overview

The global stagnation of the Environmental Footprint (EF) score per 100 grams of product, despite minor fluctuations over time, indicates that the overall environmental quality of food consumed at home has remained largely unchanged during the observed period, as we can see in (Figure 18). However, while the overall EF score remains stable, the distribution of household scores across different percentiles reveals notable disparities. The 95th percentile (dashed orange line) shows a consistent decline from 2002 to 2006, followed by a modest upward trend with minor fluctuations until 2019. This suggests that the most environmentally impactful households have slightly worsened their scores over time, potentially due to shifts in consumption patterns. In the other hand, the 5th percentile (dashed purple line) remains consistently low, indicating that households with the least environmental impact have maintained their behavior throughout the period. The 25th and 75th percentiles also exhibit relative stability.

Figure 18: Average EF Score by household per year with their 5%, 25%, 75% and 95% percentiles

In Figure 19 we can observe the evolution over time of the quality and the quantity of the main environmental indicators used to compute the score. The first column of graphs represents the quality of each component that is given by Equation 18, which illustrates the average environmental indicator for every 100g of food. As we can see, four of the indicators (Climate change, Air particles emissions, Land use, and Acidification) have a similar downward trend over the years, signifying the environmental quality in terms of these aspects have slightly improved. Contrarily, for the quality of the Water and Energy Depletion there has been a rather constant upward trend, which implies a worsening in this ecological aspects. However, in the third column of graphs, we can see in the index evolution that these fluctuations in the quality do not surpass the margin of 5%, meaning that the environmental quality has stayed relatively stable over the years. Regarding the quantity dimension, which is expressed as the daily average of the environmental indicator, following equation Equation 19, we see the same trend across all indicators, where there has been between a 15% and 20% increase from 2002 to 2019. This homogeneous tendency is due to the fact that to calculate this evolution, the indicators are multiplied by the quantity of food consumed at home, which is why most of indicators' behavior resembles the quantity index evolution seen in Figure 5.

Figure 19: Time evolution of the main environmental indicators concerning the EF Score in terms of the average content and daily intake of food products consumed at home: Climate Change or CO2 emissions, Air Particles, Water Depletion, Land Use, Energy Depletion, and Acidification. Note: The daily intake values are expressed in per capita male equivalent. The Index graphical representations is taking 2002 as the base year.

Figure 20 presents the EF score and its main components as indexes, facilitating a clearer comparison between them. The indexes measure the yearly average composition of each environmental indicator and its evolution through time. Water depletion and energy depletion show a consistent upward trend, as previously stated, indicating increasing efficiency or reduced impact in these areas. Notably, land use exhibits the most negative trend, suggesting that the impact on land resources has decreased over time. Lastly, acidification and air particles emissions remain relatively stable over time, mirroring the stagnation observed in the overall EF index. The mixed trends of improvement in some areas (e.g., water and energy depletion) and deterioration in others (e.g., land use) appear to balance each other out, leading to the relatively unchanged score.

Figure 20: EF Score and its main components Indexes (Average content per 100g of products)
 Note: The Indices takes 2002 as the base year.

6.2 Environmental footprint by food categories

Lastly, to understand the environmental impact of food consumption across different food classifications, the Figure 21 illustrates the EF score of various food categories¹⁷, highlighting the variability in their environmental impact. Among all categories, Meat, Fish & Eggs exhibit the highest EF score, with a median above 1.0 and a wide range extending towards 2.0, confirming their significant environmental burden. In contrast, Fruits & Vegetables and Plant-based Proteins display relatively low EF scores, indicating their more sustainable nature. Other food groups such as Dairy, Fats, and Ready-made Meals show moderate EF scores, but with considerable variability, suggesting differences in the environmental impact of specific products within these categories. Notably, Sweet

¹⁷From the 12 main food classifications we are excluding Drinks and Other Products as they contained extreme heterogeneous food products within the categories or classifications.

Products and Sauces & Condiments exhibit lower EF scores with minimal variation, suggesting a relatively consistent environmental impact across products in these categories.

Figure 21: Distribution of the Household's average EF Score over the whole period (2002-2019) by the main food classifications

7 Sustainable healthy diets

7.1 General overview

This section is dedicated to the descriptive analysis of the data, with a focus into the relationship between nutritional and environmental quality. To explore this connection, we constructed scatter plot graphics that represent the NPM scores alongside the EF scores for various households across all available years. These visual representations provide a clear depiction of the data, enabling us to assess both the sign and magnitude of the relationship. Furthermore, they allow us to observe how this relation evolves and varies depending on the specific classification of foods, offering deeper insights into the interconnection between nutritional and environmental factors.

Figure 22 illustrates the general relationship between the NPM and EF score, where each data point represents the household's average score in a specific year. The regression line superimposed on the scatter plot provides insight into the general trend between these two variables. The graph reveals a weak positive relationship between the EF and NPM scores, as suggested by the slight upward slope of the regression line. This indicates that households with less healthy diets (higher NPM scores) tend to have higher environmental footprints (higher EF scores), although the relationship appears to be quite weak, given the wide dispersion of points around the regression line. The dense clustering near the center of the plot suggests that most households have moderate EF and NPM

scores, while relatively few have extreme values for either metric.

Figure 22: NPM and EF score scatter plot relationship

Nonetheless, Figure 23 shows a much clearer positive relationship between the average content of calories and emissions of CO₂ per 100g of food. The regression line, with its strong upward slope, indicates that as the daily calorie intake of households increases, the associated CO₂ emissions from their food consumption also tend to increase. This suggests that higher-calorie diets are typically linked to food with a larger environmental impact in terms of CO₂ emissions.

Figure 23: Scatterplot calories and CO₂ relationship (per 100g content of food)

The denser clustering of points around the regression line suggests a consistent relationship, with outliers being relatively rare. Households with low calorie intake tend to have lower CO2 emissions, whereas households with very high calorie intake contribute disproportionately to higher emissions. This pattern highlights the importance of addressing not only the quality but also the quantity of food consumption in discussions about dietary sustainability and environmental impact.

7.2 By food categories

Lastly, Figure 24 shows the scatterplot for the main five food classifications. For cereals, the relationship is weak, with most data points concentrated around low to moderate EF scores and low NPM scores. This indicates that cereals generally have a low environmental footprint and exhibit minimal variation in healthiness relative to their environmental impact. Similarly, Fruits & vegetables show a lack of correlation between NPM and EF scores, with most points clustered in the low EF and NPM regions. This highlights that Fruits & vegetables are both environmentally sustainable and nutritionally healthy choices, emphasizing their dual benefit.

Figure 24: NPM and EF score scatter plot relationship by the 5 main Food Classifications

For meat, fish, & eggs, the trend line suggests a slightly negative relationship between the NPM and EF scores. This indicates that as the environmental footprint of the food intake increases, the healthiness of the diet may slightly improve. This could be partially explained by healthier raw meat products that have a higher environmental impact, contrary to unhealthier ultra-processed meat products. Finally, in the case of dairy and sweet products, a positive correlation is observed, with higher EF scores linked to less healthy diets. However, in the case of dairy products, a non-linear relationship appears to emerge, in contrast to sweet products, where a more evident, though weaker, positive linear relationship can be observed.

8 Who purchases what: Demographics and sustainable healthy diets

8.1 Overview by demographics

In the following section, we analyze and compare key metrics across specific socio-demographic variables. This approach aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the socio-demographic determinants that may influence dietary choices at both the individual and household levels. Our focus will center on seven critical demographic variables: age group, Body Mass Index (BMI), presence of children under 6 years old, social class, inactivity, region, and education. For each of these characteristics, we will systematically compare several dimensions, including the quantity of food consumed, deflated expenditures, and price per kilogram of food, as well as the the NPM, EF scores and the percentage of meals taken at home.

Age Group

Figure 25 shows that older households (50+) consistently consume more food quantity per capita compared to younger groups, reflected by their higher daily average. However, something that can explain partially this difference is the fact that the average percentage of meals at home is higher for older groups, where sometimes it surpasses even the 100%, meaning that more people than the members of the household are taking meals at home (e.g. when grandparents invite their grandchildren to dinner or lunch). This trend also aligns with their higher expenditures on food, and the price per kilogram, suggesting then a positive relationship between the age and the main purchase variables.

Figure 25: Quantity, Expenditures, Price, Percentage of meals-at-home, NPM and EF score by Age group

Note: Household's average values in per capita male equivalent. Price and expenditures deflated to 2002 prices.

In terms of healthiness, as indicated by the NPM score, the older age group demonstrates healthier choices (lower NPM scores) than younger groups (+100%), particularly the ≤ 34 and 35-49 groups, whose NPM scores are notably higher, implying less healthy diets. The environmental impact, represented by the EF scores, shows that the older age group (65+) maintains slightly higher EF scores, indicating a larger environmental footprint compared to the younger groups, particularly ≤ 34 . However, the variation across groups is relatively modest compared to the differences in the NPM score, with a small range that goes only from 0.4 to 0.45, a 10% difference.

BMI Group

Figure 26 illustrates that obese and overweight households consistently consume the highest daily average food quantity per capita, with similar trends, followed by normal groups, highlighting a positive correlation between BMI and food intake, as expected. Additionally, overweight and obese households have a higher percentage of meals taken at home than normal BMI households, which can increase partially the gap in the quantity consumed. Regarding the other consumption variables, obese and overweight households exhibit higher food expenditures, surpassing normal households, even though the price per kilogram of food is relatively similar across BMI categories, with a slight lower price paid by obese households.

Figure 26: Quantity, Expenditures, Price, Percentage of meals-at-home, NPM and EF score by BMI group

Note: Household's average values in per capita male equivalent. Price and expenditures deflated to 2002 prices.

In terms of the nutrition quality, obese households show significantly higher values, indicating less healthy dietary choices. Overweight and normal households seem to have a closely similar nutritional quality of food purchases until 2014, when the deterioration of the NPM score for overweight households increased. While obese and overweight households consume similar quantities, the critical distinction arises with obese households, whose dietary quality is markedly worse. This underscores that the disparity between obese and overweight groups lies more in the nutritional quality than in the quantity of consumption. Lastly, regarding the environmental footprint, as shown by the EF scores, obese and overweight households again display the highest scores, suggesting that their dietary patterns carry a larger environmental footprint.

Children Group (less than 6 y/0)

In Figure 27 we can see how households without children consistently show higher daily average food quantities consumed and higher food expenditures compared to households with children. This indicates that households without children allocate more per capita resources to food consumption, however it is worth mentioning that the average percentage of meals-at-home is considerably lower for the households with children throughout the years, which can explain a share of this difference we see in consumption. Regarding the prices, households with children appear to purchase slightly cheaper food, especially in recent years, potentially reflecting budget-conscious decision-making.

Figure 27: Quantity, Expenditures, Price, Percentage of meals-at-home, NPM and EF score by Child group

Note: Household’s average values in per capita male equivalent. Price and expenditures deflated to 2002 prices.

The NPM reveals that households with children consistently have higher (less healthy) scores than those without children, with the gap widening over time. This suggests that households with children under six may prioritize cost or convenience over nutritional quality. Lastly, for the environmental impact, households without children exhibit slightly higher EF scores throughout the period, indicating a marginally larger environmental footprint.

Social-class

Figure 28 illustrates how higher social classes (Well-off and Upper middle) consistently show greater food expenditures and higher price per kilogram of food, indicating access to more expensive diets. In contrast, the Modest group demonstrates the lowest expenditures and food quantities per capita, reflecting economic constraints. Notably, while food expenditures have risen steadily across all groups, food quantity declined for lower-income groups after 2012, possibly due to worsening economic conditions or dietary shifts toward cheaper, calorie-dense options.

Figure 28: Quantity, Expenditures, Price, Percentage of meals-at-home, NPM and EF score by Social class

Note: Household's average values in per capita male equivalent. Price and expenditures deflated to 2002 prices.

Regarding the nutritional and environmental quality, the Well-off group exhibits healthier diets (lower NPM scores) probably due to their ability to afford higher-quality, nutrient-dense, and minimally processed foods, which are often more expensive. Conversely, the Modest group has higher NPM scores, reflecting less healthy diets dominated by low priced, processed and high-caloric food. Nonetheless, the economic disparity does not extends to environmental impacts, where throughout the years there is not a clear trend that allows us to determine which group have a higher or lower impact, and the differences between the scores are considerably small, varying from 0.41 to 0.44.

Inactivity

As stated in Section 1, the "Inactivity" variable represents if at least one person in the household is either retired or unemployed. Figure 29 illustrates that households with at least one inactive member consistently exhibit higher daily average food consumption and expenditures per capita compared to those with no inactive members. Notably, both demographic groups exhibit rising prices per kilogram of food, however the price is consistently higher for households with at least one inactive member, indicating a preference for higher-quality or more diverse food options. Especially for the retired individuals, as we observed in the analysis of the age groups, where older individuals (mostly retired) had higher expenditures and prices than the other younger groups. Also, following the same logic, we can observe that the percentage of meals taken at home is considerably higher

for those with at least one member inactive (similar as the old population) than for the no inactive households, partially explaining the gap in quantities and expenditures between the groups.

Figure 29: Quantity, Expenditures, Price, Percentage of meals-at-home, NPM and EF score by Inactivity

Note: Household’s average values in per capita male equivalent. Price and expenditures deflated to 2002 prices.

The NPM score indicates that households with no inactive members consume less healthy diets over time, as their NPM scores increase steadily. In contrast, households with at least one inactive member maintain significantly lower NPM scores, reflecting healthier dietary choices. This could suggest that increased time availability or different lifestyle habits among inactive individuals may facilitate more health-conscious food purchasing and preparation. Lastly, the EF score shows that households with at least one inactive member have slightly higher environmental impacts than those with no inactive members.

Region

Households in regions such as Paris the North and the South East consistently consume larger food quantities and allocate higher daily expenditures compared to other regions, as we can appreciate in Figure 30. Conversely, regions like the East and Center West display lower levels of consumption and expenditures. Over time, expenditures have risen across all regions, reflecting the increasing price per kilogram of food. The price per kilogram is notably higher in Paris, which reflects the high general cost of living of the capital.

Figure 30: Quantity, Expenditures, Price, Percentage of meals-at-home, NPM and EF score by Region

Note: Household’s average values in per capita male equivalent. Price and expenditures deflated to 2002 prices.

The NPM score reveals regional differences in diet healthiness. Paris and the South East maintain lower NPM scores over time, indicating healthier dietary patterns, while regions such as the Center West and North have comparatively higher NPM scores, reflecting lower nutritional quality. Finally, in contrast, the EF score does not exhibit a clear trend or consistent differences between regions in which the changes in the scores over time are relatively small.

Education

In Figure 31, first we can observe how the daily average quantity of food consumed is evidently higher for the households with less education (Bac or Court or less than Bac). This can be partially explained by the higher share of meals taken at home for these groups, which are relatively higher than the most educated groups (Bac+2 and more than Bac+2). The expenditures follow a similar trend, where the less educated groups spend in average more money per day in food at-home. In the other hand, the average price per kg paid by the most educated group is relatively higher, similar to those with a higher social-class, however we can observe an increasing trend in all groups.

Figure 31: Quantity, Expenditures, Price, Percentage of meals-at-home, NPM and EF score by Education

Note: Household's average values in per capita male equivalent. Price and expenditures deflated to 2002 prices.

Regarding the nutritional and environmental quality, the NPM score evolution shows that individuals with lower education levels tend to have higher NPM scores, indicating a diet of lower nutritional quality, while those with higher education, particularly the More than Bac+2 group, maintain lower scores, reflecting healthier food choices. Similarly, the EF score is generally lower for the more educated groups, suggesting that their food consumption patterns have a lower environmental impact. These findings align with expectations, as individuals with higher education levels tend to be more conscious of both nutritional quality and environmental sustainability when making food choices.

8.2 Demographics by food categories

Based on the circle graphical representations presented in Section 3, Figure 32 to Figure 36 exhibit the fundamental difference between opposite demographic groups (e.g. Old-young, Obese-Normal BMI) in terms of their food consumption across the main food categories and its nutritional quality implied in the intersection between the "A" points and "C" points.

Figure 32 compares food consumption habits between old and young age households. Colored circles represent the older age group, while black-outlined circles denote the younger group, with circle sizes indicating the relative quantity consumed. A key trend observed is that younger individuals tend to consume more fruits & vegetables and meat, fish & eggs and less cereals, dairy, sweet, and ready-

made meals products, as we can see in the sizes of the circles. Furthermore, the consumption of dairy products is considerably higher for dairy products but lower for meat, fish & eggs. Regarding the intersection between "A" points and "C" points, we cannot see any significant shifts for the most consumed categories, however there are considerable changes in the location of the sweet products and oils & fats, where old groups exhibit less nutritional quality or less "healthy" points.

Figure 32: Average A (Unhealthy) points vs C (Healthy) points comparison between old and young age cohorts across the main food classifications

Note: Colored dots represents the average of the intersection between the "A" points and "C" points for each food classification. The sizes of the circles are based on the relative quantity (%) consumed per individual for each food classification.

Figure 33 illustrates the differences in food consumption habits between individuals with normal BMI and those with obese BMI. The results indicate that the differences between the two groups are minimal in terms of both the size of the circles and the positioning of the A and C intersections, suggesting that overall consumption patterns do not vary significantly between them.

Figure 33: Average A (Unhealthy) points vs C (Healthy) points comparison between obese and normal BMI across the main food classifications

Note: Colored dots represents the average of the intersection between the "A" points and "C" points for each food classification. The sizes of the circles are based on the relative quantity (%) consumed per individual for each food classification.

Figure 34 highlights the differences in food consumption habits between households with at least one child of less than 6 years old and those without children. A noticeable pattern emerges in the variation of circle sizes, indicating changes in the relative quantity of food consumed. Households with children tend to consume larger quantities of fruits & vegetables and meat, fish & eggs, as reflected in the increased size of the color circles compared to those without children (black outlined circles). On the contrary, the relative consumption of dairy products is larger in households with no children. Additionally, the shifts in the intersection points of A and C values are especially noticeable for the oils & fats and sweet products.

Figure 34: Average A (Unhealthy) points vs C (Healthy) points comparison between 1 children or more and no children across the main food classifications

Note: Colored dots represents the average of the intersection between the "A" points and "C" points for each food classification. The sizes of the circles are based on the relative quantity (%) consumed per individual for each food classification.

Figure 35 compares food consumption habits between the well-off and modest economic classes. One of the most notable differences is that the well-off class consumes significantly more fruits and vegetables, as indicated by the larger green circle for this category compared to the modest class. This suggests that higher-income households prioritize healthier food choices. Additionally, the well-off class tends to consume slightly less relative quantity of dairy and sweet products. While meat, fish & eggs consumption appears relatively similar between both groups, the well-off class exhibits slightly lower unhealthy (A) points for this category, placing it below the threshold.

Figure 35: Average A (Unhealthy) points vs C (Healthy) points comparison between well-off class and modest class across the main food classifications

Note: Colored dots represents the average of the intersection between the "A" points and "C" points for each food classification. The sizes of the circles are based on the relative quantity (%) consumed per individual for each food classification.

Finally, Figure 36 compares food consumption habits between individuals with at least one inactive person in their household and those with no inactive members. One of the most notable differences is that households with at least one inactive member tend to consume more sweet and dairy products, as indicated by the larger purple circle in these categories. On the other hand, cereals, meat, fish & eggs, and fruits & vegetables are more prominent in households with no inactive members, as indicated by the larger outlined circles in these categories. The no inactive group exhibits higher healthy (C) points, particularly for sweet products and oils & fats, contrary at what happens with the sauces classification, in which the C points decreased considerably.

Figure 36: Average A (Unhealthy) points vs C (Healthy) points comparison between "at least one inactive" and "no inactive" across the main food classifications

Note: Colored dots represents the average of the intersection between the "A" points and "C" points for each food classification. The sizes of the circles are based on the relative quantity (%) consumed per individual for each food classification.

9 Econometrics

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
	Healthy Quantity	Unhealthy Quantity	Eco-friendly Quantity	Non eco-friendly Quantity	Healthy/Unhealthy Relative Quantity	Eco/Non-eco Relative Quantity
Age Cohort						
Age: > 1980 °	-	-	-	-	-	-
Age: 1960–1980	-0.10*	-0.04	-0.12	-0.03	0.00	-0.19
Age: < 1960	-0.09	-0.02	-0.07	-0.04	0.04	-0.05
Body Mass Index						
Normal °	-	-	-	-	-	-
Overweight	0.00	0.01*	0.01	0.01	-0.03	-0.01
Obese	0.01	0.03***	0.02	0.01*	-0.08**	-0.04
Children						
Children <6 y/o	0.14***	0.03***	0.14***	0.03***	0.22***	0.22***
Number of children <16 y/o	0.07***	0.04***	0.08***	0.03***	0.02	0.02*
Inactivity						
Single	0.08***	0.04***	0.08***	0.04***	0.02	-0.03
Income Class						
Modeste class °	-	-	-	-	-	-
Lower-middle class	0.04***	0.02***	0.05***	0.02***	0.02	-0.02
Upper-middle class	0.07***	0.03***	0.07***	0.02***	0.05**	-0.02
Well-off class	0.10***	0.04***	0.10***	0.03***	0.07**	-0.01
Region						
Paris °	-	-	-	-	-	-
East	0.08	0.05	0.08	0.04*	-0.14	-0.15
North	0.12*	0.05*	0.11	0.06**	-0.03	-0.19
West	0.11**	0.06**	0.12**	0.05***	-0.00	-0.07
Center-West	0.05	0.09***	0.08	0.07***	-0.25*	-0.27*
Center-East	0.08	0.04	0.08	0.05**	0.01	-0.08

South-East	0.12**	0.05	0.13**	0.04*	0.11	-0.04
South-West	0.12**	0.08**	0.13**	0.06**	-0.07	-0.14
Environmental Dummies						
Fruit tree	-0.00	0.00	-0.01	0.01*	-0.01	-0.04**
Vegetable home-production	0.01	0.01***	0.01	0.01***	-0.04**	-0.04***
Relative Price Indices						
Healthy / Unhealthy	-0.31***	0.07*	-0.23***	-0.02	-0.58***	-0.32**
Eco friendly / unfriendly	-0.28***	-0.09***	-0.37***	-0.00	-0.30***	-0.77***
Constant	1.31***	0.75***	1.52***	0.54***	1.94***	3.27***
r2	0.15	0.11	0.15	0.18	0.02	0.02
Nb obs.	92113	92113	92113	92113	92113	92113

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

° corresponds to reference variables

"Number of individuals" is not displaying in the table but is used as a control variable

	(1) NPM Score	(2) Energy	(3) Saturated Fats	(4) Sugar	(5) Sodium	(6) Fibers	(7) Proteins	(8) Fruits & Vegetables
Age Cohort								
Age: >1980 °	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Age: 1960–1980	0.03	-1.19	-0.04	-0.17	1.78	-0.04	-0.06	-0.01
Age: <1960	-0.09	-3.10	-0.15	-0.05	-2.76	-0.02	-0.23	-0.00
Body Mass Index								
Normal °	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Overweight	0.04	0.57	0.02	-0.02	1.62	-0.00	0.03	-0.00
Obese	0.12**	1.16	0.05*	-0.01	1.47	-0.02*	0.04	-0.01*
Children								
Children <6 y/o	-0.27***	-4.56***	-0.10***	-0.04	-7.90***	0.00	-0.15***	-0.00
Number of children <16 y/o	0.04*	0.59*	0.02**	0.14***	-0.82	0.01	-0.02*	-0.00
Inactivity								
Single	-0.05*	0.43	0.01	-0.03	1.99*	0.02***	0.07***	0.00
Income Class								
Modest °	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Lower-middle	0.00	-0.56	-0.01	0.02	-1.68*	-0.02**	0.00	-0.00
Upper-middle	-0.06*	-1.47**	-0.03*	-0.03	-2.73**	-0.02**	-0.00	0.00
Well-off	-0.09*	-2.10***	-0.04*	-0.10*	-3.37**	-0.03***	0.01	0.00
Region								
Paris °	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
East	0.26	4.79	0.15*	0.39*	5.73	0.05	0.08	0.00
North	-0.10	-0.47	-0.06	-0.04	2.88	0.03	0.06	0.01
West	0.15	2.25	0.10*	0.08	1.46	-0.03	0.04	-0.01
Center-West	0.37*	3.24	0.16*	-0.02	1.93	-0.08*	0.17	-0.03*
Center-East	0.16	3.13	0.07	0.03	4.53	0.02	0.09	-0.01
South-East	-0.04	0.62	0.04	-0.08	-2.83	0.00	0.03	0.01
South-West	0.23*	1.80	0.10	0.18	-0.42	-0.03	0.02	-0.01
Environmental Dummies								
Fruit tree	0.05*	0.98**	0.02*	0.06**	0.98	-0.00	0.04**	-0.00
Vegetable home-production	0.08***	1.34***	0.04***	-0.01	1.35*	-0.02**	0.06***	-0.01***
Relative Price Index								
Healthy / Unhealthy	0.38**	4.22*	0.19**	-0.12	13.01**	-0.01	0.07	-0.00
Eco friendly / unfriendly	0.24*	6.62***	0.26***	0.16	7.49	0.01	0.47***	0.01
Constant	1.42***	143.62***	2.92***	7.43***	180.35***	1.67***	5.48***	0.31***

r2	0.02	0.04	0.03	0.02	0.08	0.09	0.02	0.03
Nb obs.	92113	92113	92113	92113	92113	92113	92113	92113

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

°corresponds to reference variables

"Number of individuals" is not displaying in the table but is used as a control variable

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
	EF Score	Climate Change	Land Use	Energy Depletion	Water Depletion	Air Particles	Acidification	Water Eutrophication
Age Cohort								
Age: > 1980 °	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Age: 1960–1980	0.00	0.01	1.88	0.57	-0.08	0.01	0.00	0.00
Age: < 1960	-0.00	-0.06	-3.14	0.20	0.02	-0.00	-0.00	-0.00
Body Mass Index								
Normal °	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Overweight	0.00	0.02	1.23	0.09	-0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00
Obese	0.00	0.03	2.20	0.07	-0.05*	0.00	0.00	0.00
Children								
Children <6 y/o	-0.01***	-0.07***	-2.98***	-0.27***	-0.10***	-0.01***	-0.00***	-0.01***
Number of children <16 y/o	-0.00**	-0.02*	-1.56***	-0.20***	-0.00	-0.00***	-0.00***	-0.00**
Inactivity								
Single	0.00**	0.03**	1.92*	0.21**	0.01	0.00**	0.00**	0.01***
Single	-0.01***	-0.07***	-4.90***	-0.56***	0.08***	-0.01***	-0.00***	-0.01***
Income Class								
Modeste °	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Lower-middle	0.00	0.02	1.23	-0.02	-0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.00
Upper-middle	0.00	0.03*	1.56	-0.02	-0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Well-off	0.00	0.04	2.18	-0.09	-0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Region								
Paris °	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
East	0.00	0.01	0.77	-0.10	0.19	0.00	0.00	0.01
North	0.00	0.02	1.66	0.35	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00
West	0.00	0.01	-0.20	0.32	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.01*
Center-West	0.01	0.05	2.60	0.79	-0.08	0.01	0.00	0.02*
Center-East	0.01	0.07	5.12	0.65	-0.04	0.01	0.00	0.01
South-East	0.00	0.05	2.08	0.41	-0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01
South-West	0.00	-0.00	-1.17	0.18	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.00
Environmental Dummies								
Fruit tree	0.00**	0.03**	1.83**	0.08	0.00	0.00**	0.00**	0.00**
Vegetable home-production	0.00***	0.03***	2.33***	0.09	-0.01	0.00***	0.00***	0.00***
Relative Price Indices								
Healthy / Unhealthy	0.01	0.08	0.37	0.53	-0.05	0.01	0.00	0.01
Eco friendly / unfriendly	0.04***	0.32***	14.56***	1.65***	0.27***	0.03***	0.00***	0.04***
Constant	0.41***	3.33***	158.48***	34.80***	4.45***	0.30***	0.04***	0.54***
r2	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.04	0.04	0.01	0.01	0.04
Nb obs.	92113	92113	92113	92113	92113	92113	92113	92113

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$

°corresponds to reference variables

"Number of individuals" is not displaying in the table but is used as a control variable

Age cohort

Individuals that were born from 1960–1980 consume significantly less healthy quantities ($\beta = -0.10, p < 0.05$) compared to those born after 1980. We find no significant effect on the nutritional and environmental qualities, and their components, of food purchases.

Body Mass Index

Overweight and obese individuals consume significantly more unhealthy food ($\beta = 0.01, p < 0.05$ for overweight; $\beta = 0.03, p < 0.001$ for obese) and obese individuals have a higher NPM score, meaning a lower nutritional quality ($\beta = 0.12, p < 0.001$), due to higher saturated fat content ($\beta = 0.05, p < 0.05$) and lower fiber ($\beta = -0.02, p < 0.05$) and fruit and vegetables ($\beta = -0.01, p < 0.05$) contents. Even controlling for other socio-demographic factors, we come to the same conclusion as we saw previously in the demographic descriptive analysis, in which overweight and obese consume more (unhealthy) quantities than normal BMI, and only obese households have a significantly lower nutritional quality. The obesity status does not affect the environmental quality, except on water depletion ($\beta = -0.05, p < 0.05$), possibly due to lower FV consumption.

Children

Households with children under 6 years old purchase significantly more healthy food ($\beta = 0.14, p < 0.001$), and more unhealthy food but in a lesser extent ($\beta = 0.03, p < 0.001$). Similarly, they consumer more eco-friendly ($\beta = 0.14, p < 0.001$) and non-eco friendly food ($\beta = 0.03, p < 0.001$). Regarding the nutritional quality, we observe these households with children under 6 years old have a lower NPM score ($\beta = -0.28, p < 0.001$), meaning a higher nutritional quality, and can be explained by the negative coefficients on the content of unhealthy nutrients, such as the energy, saturated fats and sodium. The EF score is smaller for these households ($\beta = -0.01, p < 0.001$) and the environmental quality decreased for all components of the EF score, aspect we can perceive in their negative coefficients.. We obtain the same results for the number of children under 16 years old, except that we observe a higher NPM score, meaning that more children deteriorate the nutritional quality of food purchases particularly for its energy, saturated fat, and sugar.

Inactivity

Having at least one inactive member in the household corresponds to an increase in the consumption of healthy food ($\beta = 0.08, p < 0.001$) and unhealthy food ($\beta = 0.04, p < 0.001$), and same effects can be found on eco-friendly or non-eco friendly quantities. "At least one inactive" households consume more fiber and proteins-dense food ($\beta = 0.02, p < 0.01$) and ($\beta = 0.07, p < 0.001$), which can be reflected in the negative coefficient of the NPM score ($\beta = -0.05, p < 0.05$), even though they consume on average more sodium food ($\beta = 2.03, p < 0.05$). Inactive individuals contribute more to the environmental impact with a higher EF score and higher environmental components, except for water depletion.

Single

Single individuals buy more healthy and unhealthy food compared to non-single ones ($\beta = 0.19, p < 0.001$ and $\beta = 0.10, p < 0.001$, respectively) and something similar occurs for the purchases of eco-friendly and non eco-friendly food ($\beta = 0.21, p < 0.001$ and $\beta = 0.08, p < 0.001$). They also have a higher NPM score ($\beta = 0.14, p < 0.001$), that can be partially explained by a higher content of energy, saturated fats, sugar and sodium contents in food purchases, even though we can observe as well a higher fiber content. Single individuals have a better environmental quality of food purchases due to a negative effect on the EF score ($\beta = -0.01, p < 0.001$) and this effect is significant for all the environmental components.

Income class

Wealthier households purchase more healthy food ($\beta = 0.10$ for well-off class, 0.07 for upper-middle, 0.04 for lower-middle; all $p < 0.001$) but also more unhealthy food ($\beta = 0.04$ for well-off, 0.03 for upper-middle, 0.02 for lower-middle; all $p < 0.001$). The same occurs for the purchases of eco-friendly and non eco-friendly purchases. Globally, the nutritional quality is positively correlated with income (due to lower NPM score, lower energy, saturated fat, sugar, and sodium content). We find no significant effect of income on all the environmental indicators.

Environmental Dummies

Having a fruit tree signifies a higher consumption of not-eco friendly food products ($\beta = 0.01, p < 0.01$). If a household has any type of vegetable home-production, they would purchase more unhealthy and less eco friendly quantity of food ($\beta = 0.01, p < 0.001$ and $\beta = 0.01, p < 0.001$, respectively), aspect that could be explained by the fact that as they have the possibility of producing vegetables at-home, they would not need to buy them at stores, and the relative quantity of unhealthy or less-eco friendly food products would increase. Regarding the nutritional quality, having a fruit tree at home or producing domestically vegetables translate in having a higher NPM score ($\beta = 0.05, p < 0.05$ and $\beta = 0.08, p < 0.001$, respectively), therefore having worse "healthy" purchases compared to the households without these features. We can also see the increase on most of the average contents of the "negative" components of the NPM score, such as the case with the energy, sodium and saturated fats. For the environmental quality we observe that the possession of a fruit tree or a vegetable home production correspond to a higher EF score and worse environmental indicators.

Relative price indices

The relative price of healthy / unhealthy food has a strong negative effect ($\beta = -0.31, p < 0.001$) on quantities of healthy food purchases and a positive effect on unhealthy food purchases ($\beta = 0.07, p < 0.05$). It has a positive effect on the NPM score ($\beta = 0.30, p < 0.01$), meaning an increase in the healthy relative price deteriorates the nutritional quality of food purchases. This effect is particularly

due to the strong effect on the sodium content of food purchases ($\beta = 13.02, p < 0.001$). The increase of this relative price has a significant negative effect on the eco-friendly quantities consumed. The relative price of eco-friendly / non eco-friendly food has a strong negative effect ($\beta = -0.37, p < 0.001$) on the quantity of eco-friendly food purchases but non significant effect on the quantity of non-eco-friendly food purchases. Regarding the nutritional aspect, an increase in this relative price signifies an augmentation on the NPM score ($\beta = -0.24, p < 0.05$), due to an increase in calories, saturated fats and proteins, meaning that it should increase meat consumption. Lastly, We observe a decrease in environmental quality when the relative price goes up, as the EF score ($\beta = 0.04, p < 0.001$) and the other main environmental indicators have positive and significant coefficients.

10 Conclusion

This report seek to examine the evolution of food consumption in France from 2002 to 2019, focusing on its nutritional and environmental qualities through the lenses of the NPM (Nutrient Profiling Model) and EF (Environmental Footprint) scores. By combining graphical analysis and econometric modeling, we help to understand not only how food consumption patterns have changed over time, but also how these changes intersect with public health and sustainability.

The results reveal a subtle evolution of food consumption. While overall quantities and expenditures remained relatively stable, a degradation in nutritional quality was observed. This deterioration is mainly driven by an increase in sodium and, to a lesser extent, saturated fats and energy content. Encouragingly, there have been slight improvements in certain components, such as fiber and fruit and vegetable content, and a marginal decline in sugar content.

From an environmental perspective, the EF score remained relatively stable throughout the period, with only a weak positive correlation to the NPM score. This suggests that less healthy diets tend to be slightly more environmentally detrimental, though the relationship is not strongly pronounced. Moreover, higher calorie diets are linked with greater CO2 emissions, highlighting an important convergence between nutritional and environmental concerns.

The panel data analysis corroborates and enriches these findings from the graphical analysis. We identify that nutritional quality significantly varies across demographic and socioeconomic groups. Older individuals, wealthier households, and families with young children tend to consume healthier diets. In contrast, obese individuals and those from more modest income groups exhibit poorer dietary profiles. While income levels are closely associated with nutritional quality, their influence on environmental outcomes appears insignificant. On the other hand, relative prices have a significant impact, where higher prices of healthy or eco-friendly foods correspond to worse nutritional and

environmental outcomes, highlighting the role of affordability in shaping consumption patterns.

These insights carry direct implications for public policy. The deterioration of nutritional quality over time and the disparities observed across population groups call for targeted measures. Policies that support lower-income households in accessing nutrient-dense and sustainably produced foods are pertinent within this context. Fiscal tools such as subsidies on healthy and eco-friendly foods or taxes on ultra-processed, high-sodium products could help shift consumption behaviors. Moreover, increasing awareness about the dual benefits of healthier diets, not only for individual well-being but also for environmental sustainability, can be instrumental in fostering long-term change.

References

- Bonnet, C., Dubois, P., and Orozco, V. (2014). Household food consumption, individual calories intake and obesity in france. *Empirical Economics*, 46(3):1143–1166.
- Department of Health (2011). Nutrient profiling technical guidance. Published in electronic PDF format only.
- FAO/WHO (2004). Human energy requirements. report of a joint fao/who/unu expert consultation. rome 17-24 october 2001. *FAO Food and Nutrition Technical Report series 1*.
- Institut National de la Statistique et des Études Économiques (INSEE) (2024). Indice des prix à la consommation - ensemble des ménages - france (ipc).
- Rayner, M. and Scarborough, P. (2009). The UK ofcom nutrient profiling model. *Department of Public Health, University of Oxford*.
- Spiteri, M., Bonnet, C., Bouamra-Mechemache, Z., Réquillart, V., De Mouzon, O., and Orozco, V. (2023). ClasSFood, a food classification for sustainability studies.

A Additional Graphical Representations

Figure 37: Kantar and Insee Food Inflation Rates Comparison

Impact Category	Weighting Set (A)	Robustness (B)	Coefficients (C = A × B)	Final Weighting
Climate change	12.90	0.87	11.18	21.06
Ozone depletion	5.58	0.60	3.35	6.31
Human toxicity, cancer effects	6.80	0.17	1.13	2.13
Human toxicity, non-cancer effects	5.88	0.17	1.00	1.84
Particulate matter	5.49	0.87	4.76	8.96
Ionizing radiation, human health	5.70	0.47	2.66	5.01
Photochemical ozone formation, human health	4.76	0.53	2.54	4.78
Acidification	4.94	0.67	3.29	6.20
Eutrophication, terrestrial	2.95	0.67	1.97	3.71
Eutrophication, freshwater	3.19	0.47	1.49	2.80
Eutrophication, marine	2.94	0.53	1.57	2.96
Ecotoxicity freshwater	6.12	0.31	1.92	3.61
Land use	9.04	0.47	4.22	7.94
Water use	9.69	0.47	4.55	8.51
Resource use, minerals and metals	6.68	0.60	4.01	7.55
Resource use, fossils	7.37	0.60	4.42	8.32

Table 8: Weighting factors for the calculation of the Environmental Footprint (EF) score.

Food Type	Quantity (%)	Expenditures (%)	Price per kg (in €)	Avg NPM Score	Avg EF Score
Unprocessed Fruits	10.2%	5.1%	1.75	-6.0	0.26
Whole Milk	7.8%	1.5%	0.65	-0.9	0.15
Unprocessed Vegetables	7.7%	4.2%	1.90	-8.0	0.15
Wines	3.8%	3.2%	2.87	1.0	0.18
Yogurts	3.5%	1.8%	1.77	1.7	0.29
Fruit Juices	3.3%	1.2%	1.19	-4.0	0.15
Colas	3.0%	0.7%	0.79	-6.0	0.08
Potatoes and Tubers	2.6%	0.6%	0.83	-6.0	0.23
Processed Pork Meats	2.5%	6.2%	8.66	16.6	1.21
Beers	2.4%	1.1%	1.63	0.0	0.12
Cow or Buffalo Cheeses	2.3%	5.1%	7.59	19.3	0.53
Processed Vegetables	2.3%	1.8%	2.77	-8.0	0.36
Fruit Nectars	2.1%	0.5%	0.80	0.9	0.07
Dairy Desserts	1.4%	1.2%	2.94	4.7	0.36
Cottage Cheese	1.4%	0.9%	2.24	0.2	0.32
Baby Food	1.3%	1.5%	4.06	0.0	0.30
Eggs	1.2%	1.0%	2.79	11.0	0.59
Pasta	1.1%	0.6%	1.74	-3.0	0.69
Baked Goods	1.0%	0.9%	3.07	7.0	0.24
Cooked Fruits	1.0%	0.9%	2.93	-2.1	0.32

Table 9: The 20 most consumed food types and their main associated metrics.

Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
Cereal Products	Cereals, Pasta, Rice	Pasta Rice Cereals		
	Bread, Bakery Products, Flours, Dough	Bread Bakery Products Flours Dough		
Fruits & Vegetables	Vegetables	Unprocessed Vegetables Processed Vegetables	Vegetable Purees Fresh Vegetable Soups Dehydrated Vegetable Soups	
	Potatoes or Other Tubers	Unprocessed Potatoes or Other Tubers Processed Potatoes or Other Tubers Cooked Potatoes or Other Tubers	French Fries Fresh Mashed Potatoes Flaked Mashed Potatoes	
	Fruits	Unprocessed Fruits Processed Fruits Cooked Fruits	Fruit Salads Fruit Syrup Dried Fruits Compotes	
	Legumes	Unprocessed Legumes Processed Legumes Cooked Legumes	Legume Purees Fresh Legume Soups Dehydrated Legume Soups	
	Nuts			
	Beef	Unprocessed Beef Processed Beef	Ground Beef Other Processed Beef	
	Veal	Unprocessed Veal Processed Veal	Ground Veal Other Processed Veal	
	Lamb, Goat	Unprocessed Lamb, Goat Processed Lamb, Goat		
	Chicken	Unprocessed Chicken Processed Chicken	Chicken Ham Other Processed Chicken	
	Turkey	Unprocessed Turkey Processed Turkey	Turkey Ham Other Processed Turkey	
Meats, Fish & Eggs	Other Poultry	Unprocessed Other Poultry Processed Other Poultry		
	Pork	Unprocessed Pork Processed Pork	Cooked Pork Ham and Shoulders Raw or Dry Pork Ham Dry Pork Sausages Pork Pâtés or Rillettes Pork Sausages or Sausage Meat Pork Bacon or Bellies Other Processed Pork	
	Other Meats	Unprocessed Other Meats Processed Other Meats		
	Mixed Meats	Unprocessed Mixed Meats Processed Mixed Meats		
	Cooked Meats or Poultry			
	Fish, Shellfish, Mollusks	Unprocessed Fish Processed Fish Unprocessed Shellfish, Mollusks Processed Shellfish, Mollusks	Smoked Fish Other Processed Fish	
	Cooked Fish, Shellfish, Mollusks			
	Eggs			
	Cooked Eggs			
	Dairy Products	Milks	Natural Milks Flavored Milks Concentrated Milks Powdered Milks	
Yogurts			Natural Yogurts Sweetened Yogurts Flavored Yogurts Fruit Yogurts <1% Fat	Natural Yogurts <1% Fat Natural Yogurts 1-3% Fat Natural Yogurts >3% Fat Sweetened Yogurts <1% Fat Sweetened Yogurts 1-3% Fat Sweetened Yogurts >3% Fat Flavored Yogurts <1% Fat Flavored Yogurts 1-3% Fat Flavored Yogurts >3% Fat Fruit Yogurts <1% Fat Fruit Yogurts 1-3% Fat Fruit Yogurts >3% Fat
Yogurts, Desserts, Fresh Cheeses, Petit-Suisse			Natural Fresh Cheeses, Petit-Suisse	Natural Fresh Cheeses, Petit-Suisse <1% Fat Natural Fresh Cheeses, Petit-Suisse 1-5% Fat Natural Fresh Cheeses, Petit-Suisse >5% Fat Sweetened Fresh Cheeses, Petit-Suisse <1% Fat Sweetened Fresh Cheeses, Petit-Suisse 1-5% Fat Sweetened Fresh Cheeses, Petit-Suisse >5% Fat Flavored Fresh Cheeses, Petit-Suisse <1% Fat Flavored Fresh Cheeses, Petit-Suisse 1-5% Fat Flavored Fresh Cheeses, Petit-Suisse >5% Fat Fruit Fresh Cheeses, Petit-Suisse <1% Fat Fruit Fresh Cheeses, Petit-Suisse 1-5% Fat Fruit Fresh Cheeses, Petit-Suisse >5% Fat
Fresh Cheeses, Petit-Suisse			Sweetened Fresh Cheeses, Petit-Suisse Flavored Fresh Cheeses, Petit-Suisse Fruit Fresh Cheeses, Petit-Suisse	
Dairy Desserts			Mousses and Ligeroles Cream Desserts Other Dairy Desserts	
Cheeses		Cow or Buffalo Cheeses	Processed Cow or Buffalo Cheeses Fresh Unaged Cow or Buffalo Cheeses Soft Cow or Buffalo Cheeses Blue Cow or Buffalo Cheeses Pressed Cow or Buffalo Cheeses	
		Goat or Sheep Cheeses	Processed Goat or Sheep Cheeses Unprocessed Goat or Sheep Cheeses	

Sweet Products & Snacks	Sugars, Non-Chocolate Confections	Sugars and Sweeteners	Sugars and Syrups		
		Non-Chocolate Confections	Sweeteners		
	Chocolates and Chocolate Confections	Chocolate Bars	Dark Chocolate Bars	Non-Reduced Sugar Candies	
		Chocolate Bars and Confections	Milk Chocolate Bars	Reduced Sugar Candies	
	Sweet Spreads	Honeys	White Chocolate Bars	Non-Reduced Sugar Chewing Gums	
		Jams		Reduced Sugar Chewing Gums	
	Pastries, Biscuits, Viennoiseries	Syrups		Non-Reduced Sugar Other Non-Chocolate Confections	
		Other Sweet Spreads		Reduced Sugar Other Non-Chocolate Confections	
	Breakfast Cereals, Cereal Bars	Pastries			
		Biscuits			
Ice Creams, Sorbets, Frozen Desserts	Viennoiseries				
	Breakfast Cereals				
Other Sweet Products	Cereal Bars				
	Sorbets and Water Ice Creams				
Fats	Animal Fats	Milk-Based Ice Creams			
		Frozen Desserts			
	Mixed Fats	Creams		Whole Creams	
		Butters	Unsalted Butters	Non-Whole Creams	
	Vegetable Fats	Other Animal Fats	Salted Butters		
		Vegetable Oils			
		Vegetable Shortening			
		Vegetable Margarines		Margarines ≤41% Fat	
	Drinks or Beverages	Fruit Juices, Vegetable Juices, and Nectars	Other Vegetable Fats		Margarines 41-62% Fat
					Margarines >62% Fat
Waters		Fruit Juices			
		Fruit Nectars			
Non-Alcoholic Beverages		Vegetable Juices			
		Still Waters			
		Sparkling Waters			
		Colas		Standard Colas	
		Other Sodas		Reduced Sugar Colas	
		Iced Teas		Standard Other Sodas	
	Flavored Waters		Reduced Sugar Other Sodas		
	Energy and Sports Drinks		Standard Iced Teas		
	Syrups		Reduced Sugar Iced Teas		
	Alcoholic Beverages	Wines			
Beers					
Hot Beverages	Other Alcoholic Beverages				
	Spirits				
Ready-made meals	Rice-Based Prepared Meals	Ciders			
		Champagnes and Sparkling Wines			
	Pasta and Stuffed Pasta Prepared Meals	Coffees			
		Teas and Infusions			
	Semolina or Cereal-Based Prepared Meals	Hot Chocolates			
		Other Hot Beverages			
	Vegetable-Based Prepared Meals	Vegetarian Rice-Based Prepared Meals			
		Rice-Based Prepared Meals with Meat			
	Legume-Based Prepared Meals	Rice-Based Prepared Meals with Fish			
		Rice-Based Prepared Meals with Meat and Fish			
Potato-Based Prepared Meals	Vegetarian Pasta and Stuffed Pasta Prepared Meals				
	Pasta and Stuffed Pasta Prepared Meals with Meat				
Ready-to-Eat Salads	Pasta and Stuffed Pasta Prepared Meals with Fish				
	Pasta and Stuffed Pasta Prepared Meals with Meat and Fish				
Snacks	Vegetarian Semolina or Cereal-Based Prepared Meals				
	Semolina or Cereal-Based Prepared Meals with Meat				
Appetizer Products	Semolina or Cereal-Based Prepared Meals with Fish				
	Semolina or Cereal-Based Prepared Meals with Meat and Fish				
Sauces & Condiments	Vegetarian Vegetable-Based Prepared Meals				
	Vegetable-Based Prepared Meals with Meat				
Plant-Based Proteines	Vegetable-Based Prepared Meals with Fish				
	Vegetable-Based Prepared Meals with Meat and Fish				
Other Products	Vegetarian Legume-Based Prepared Meals				
	Legume-Based Prepared Meals with Meat				
Soy-Based Natural Milk Substitutes	Legume-Based Prepared Meals with Fish				
	Legume-Based Prepared Meals with Meat and Fish				
Plant-Based Yogurt, Fresh Cheese, Petit-Suisse, and Dairy Dessert Substitutes	Vegetarian Potato-Based Prepared Meals				
	Potato-Based Prepared Meals with Meat				
Plant-Based Cheese Substitutes	Potato-Based Prepared Meals with Fish				
	Potato-Based Prepared Meals with Meat and Fish				
Infant Foods	Sandwiches				
	Pizzas				
Dietary Supplements and Meal Replacements	Savory Pies				
	Other Snacks				
Baking Aids	Chips				
	Appetizer Biscuits				
Cooking Aids	Salted Peanuts and Other Nuts for Appetizers				
	Spreads				
Other Undetermined Products	Other Appetizer Products				
	Condiments				
Soy-Based Natural Milk Substitutes	Condiment Sauces	Dehydrated Condiment Sauces			
	Hot Sauces	Non-Dehydrated Condiment Sauces			
Other Natural Plant-Based Milk Substitutes	Hot Sauces	Dehydrated Hot Sauces			
	Non-Dehydrated Hot Sauces				
Natural Plant-Based Milk Substitutes	Tofus				
	Vegetarian Patties				
Flavored Plant-Based Milk Substitutes	Other Plant-Based Meat Substitutes				
	Natural Plant-Based Milk Substitutes				
Concentrated Plant-Based Milk Substitutes	Flavored Plant-Based Milk Substitutes				
	Powdered Plant-Based Milk Substitutes				
Plant-Based Yogurt Substitutes	Natural Plant-Based Milk Substitutes				
	Flavored Plant-Based Milk Substitutes				
Plant-Based Fresh Cheese, Petit-Suisse Substitutes	Natural Plant-Based Yogurt Substitutes				
	Sweetened Plant-Based Yogurt Substitutes				
Plant-Based Dairy Dessert Substitutes	Flavored Plant-Based Yogurt Substitutes				
	Fruit Plant-Based Yogurt Substitutes				
Plant-Based Fresh Cheese, Petit-Suisse Substitutes	Natural Plant-Based Fresh Cheese, Petit-Suisse Substitutes				
	Sweetened Plant-Based Fresh Cheese, Petit-Suisse Substitutes				
Fruit Plant-Based Fresh Cheese, Petit-Suisse Substitutes	Flavored Plant-Based Fresh Cheese, Petit-Suisse Substitutes				
	Fruit Plant-Based Fresh Cheese, Petit-Suisse Substitutes				

Table 11: Classification of ClasSFood categories